

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

INSTITUTE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 06.06.2022 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Prof. Devaseelan S	Chairman,
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
4. Ms. Varsha A C	Member
5. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
6. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
7. Ms. Brilly Anto	Member
8. Mrs. Priyadhersini. S	Member
9. Ms. Maureen Edwards	Member
10. Dr. Vrinda J Bhat	External Member
11. Dr. David Rosario	External Member
12. B Balaji Narayan	Industrial Expert

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 05.03.2022.
2. Changes in Internal Assessment
3. Suggested for updating in the syllabus for the next Academic Year.
4. Update the M.Sc. course Syllabus

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 05.03.2022. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Syllabus was reviewed as per the NEP 2021 in the last meeting. Hence Internal Assessment was changed accordingly. The suggestion was approved by the BOS and all the courses were asked to update the syllabus as proposed by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 3: It was suggested that the Syllabus must be updated based on the NEP for the upcoming Academic year, the credit allocation for the subjects must be changed accordingly. It was suggested to follow the new credit-based system for every courses and resolution was taken accordingly, updates and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 4: It was suggested that all the syllabus of the M.Sc. courses to be updated as per the current standards by the BOS, the resolution was taken accordingly as per the suggestions given by the stake holders and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Kavya Shettigar K, Member of Board of Studies.

Prof. Devaseelan S,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Sciences.

Members present:

Prof. Devaseelan S

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Mrs. Swathi D

Ms. Varsha A C

Ms. Kavya Shettigar K

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Ms. Brilly Anto

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